

Analysis of the Islands Tourists' Destination Information Sources and Service Satisfaction

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Abstract—The purpose of this study is to analyze the islands tourist travel information sources, as well as for the satisfaction of the tourist destination services. This study used questionnaires to the island of Taiwan to the Penghu Islands to engage in tourism activities tourist adopt the designated convenience sampling method, a total of 889 valid questionnaires were collected. After statistical analysis, this study found that: 1. tourists to the Penghu Islands travel information source for “friends and family came to Penghu”. 2. Tourists feel the service of the outlying islands of Penghu, the highest feelings of “friendly local residents”. 3. There are different demographic variables affect the tourist travel information source and service satisfaction. Based on the findings of this study not only for Penghu's tourism industry with the unit in charge of the proposed operating and suggestions for future research to other researchers.

Keywords—Island tourism, destination, travel information, service satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

DEVELOPMENT of marine tourism is an important development policy of our government, very suitable for the development of tourism and leisure based activities to the waters, surrounded by the sea in Taiwan, has abundant marine resources. However, the development of marine tourism, not only with tourism resources, relative, and service delivery is also very important. Gunn and Var [1], the study pointed out, sightseeing tourism areas of the service proper goodness projects, including: public grass-roots facilities and services (for example: traffic, water, electricity, communications, medical, etc.), catering, accommodation, retail, travel recreation opportunities, information, promotion, and so on. Penghu is Taiwan's largest outlying island, and has rich natural landscape resources, including natural resources (marine ecology, animal and plant, beach, intertidal belt, outlying islands, unique geological land type), humanities resources (historical cultural monuments), etc., to provide tourism development an important foundation for [2]. Penghu on the classification of marine tourism and recreation activities are divided into the system of the island, the South China Sea and the North Sea system, every year the people of Taiwan to the Penghu tourism, are more than one million people, is well-known in the Islands attractions.

Tourist destination is a major tourist destination of tourism, the longest stay local, and usually the highest consumption of tourists in this region, the local economy more positive impact. However, tourists began choosing travel destinations, usually

the industry who most want to know, according to Mathieson and Wall (1982) pointed out that the tourists select tourist destinations, the main process consists of five stages, namely [3]: (1) travel demand ; (2) information search; (3) determine the itinerary; line (4) preparation; (5) tourist experience and satisfaction assessment. Attitude, willingness to travel decision-making process model developed by Mayo and Jarvis [4], also shows that tourists' sources of information, generation of travel behavior has important implications. For the industry, because understanding the tourists' sources of information for your partner, your marketing efforts in this information. Travel behavior as consumers, not know much about the state of the tourist destination, tourists line will try to collect internal and external information to reduce the risk of shopping.

For Penghu's tourism, so tourists to Penghu as a tourism destination, in addition to travel information should be sufficient, the service quality of tourist attractions is necessary. However, the famous scenic spots, in addition to the natural landscape, related services and facilities dwarf the Loveluck and Wright pointed out that the service is a dynamic process, rather than a static process, and therefore required to understand the process of service delivery, as well as the relationship between customer and service [5]. In other words, such as marine tourism and recreation services, you must understand the local to provide what services, why the relationship between tourists and service, so it involves the level of service quality. Service quality refers to consumers in advance for the service expectations and perceptions after receiving services [6], most often researchers a reference to measure the dimensions of service quality; it is Parasurman, Zeithmal and Barry development the PZB scale, the scale, the main measure of service quality dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy [7]. So to understand the quality of service is good or bad, the situation of consumer satisfaction with the quality, there is the importance of consumer satisfaction or not involved in the future willingness to purchase [8]. Lee and Cheng the research Jibei Islet (2010), Chimei Islet visitors experience the value, satisfaction, and will revisit the results found that [9]: (1) the value of island visitors' experience for tourist satisfaction has a significant positive impact exists; (2) revisiting willingness, the island tourists satisfaction has a significant positive effect. By the results of the study, the value of the experience of the island after the tourists play will affect tourist satisfaction, there by affecting the willingness to revisit.

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II. PURPOSE

Tourists in the island of Taiwan, according to the above background and motivation of this study as well as Penghu tourism, in the purpose of the study can be summarized as the following two points: (A) Analysis of the situation of tourists for Penghu island sources of travel information and service satisfaction. (B) Analysis of the differences of the different demographic variables tourist travel information source and service satisfaction.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Describe Research Region

Penghu, lone island county of Taiwan, is located in the Strait off the coast of China. When low tide comes, more than one hundred isles appear, such that number of the total isles will vary. With rising tide, there are, generally speaking, 90 isles scattered between north latitude 23°12'to 23° 47' and east longitude 119°19' to 119°43'. The easternmost is called Zhamu, the westernmost Hua, the southernmost south Cimei, and the northernmost Dogiao. Hua is also the western boundary of Taiwan. Another unusual thing about Penghu is the Tropic of Cancer passing through Hoojing Isle. The Penghu County administration district includes Magong City, along with Siyu, Baisha, Husi, Wangan, and Cimei Townships [10].

B. Subject and Sampling

In the study, the Penghu National Scenic Area tourism tourists to the island of Taiwan to the object, the way of convenience sampling investigation. In July 2012 during the tourist season, tourists gathered up Chongcheng Road, downtown district and open-air coffee and lounge area to investigate, from 19:00 to 22:00. Before the survey asks respondents will of the tourists, they agreed to accept the survey; the researchers began to implement the survey. Survey a total of 1,200 questionnaires, 996 received copies back, which deducted to answer not complete or consistent with the questionnaire of 107 totals of 889 valid questionnaires.

C. Questionnaire

This research tool is divided into three parts, the first are "travel information sources scale", a total of 15 questions in this part of the scale, this scale according to Chang, Chiou, and Shih study Dahu wineries travel information source study consumer source thirds newspapers and magazines, media, internet, industry recommended, and others informed [11]. The second part is the "service quality and satisfaction scale" in this part of the Blank [12], and Gunn and Var pointed out that the basic functions required of tourist areas, including: attractive focus, services, transportation, information and promotion [1]; another reference Chang [10] research questionnaire about Penghu to the recognition of image and tourism choice; and Echtner and Ritchie tourism destination image property assessment projects, including nightlife and entertainment, shopping facilities local public works, transportation, accommodation, price level, personal safety, as well as friendly items [13]. The demographic variables of the study demographic variables, including place of residence, gender, age, marital status, education level, occupation, personal monthly income, tourism experience.

D. Data Analysis

In this study, the valid questionnaires is the use of SPSS For Windows 18.0 version statistical analysis, analysis of the steps include: 1. Used item analysis, exploratory factor analysis and Cronbach α reliability test of statistical methods to construct the reliability and validity of this research tool. 2. To analyze the frequency distribution, percentage, visitor demographic distribution of the case. 3. Used t-test analysis of tourists of different gender and marital status differences in travel information sources and service satisfaction. 4. Used one-way ANOVA analysis of different age, educational level, personal monthly income, and occupation tourists travel information sources and service satisfaction on the differences.

E. Reliability and Validity Analysis

In the scale of the sources of travel information, after exploratory factor analysis, there extracted three factors were named according to the characteristics of each factor are following options "network and government information", "mass the media" as well as "others recommended", this scale cumulative variance of 61.24%. In the service satisfaction scale, after exploratory factor analysis, there extracted three factors, the characteristics of each factor are following options are named for "entertainment and life", "traffic improve public facilities" and "friendly people and good public order", the scale cumulative variance of 55.65%. In reliability analysis, the results of the analysis show that the "travel information source" scale α value of .92; the service satisfaction scale α value of .91, from the above results, the research scale with a high degree of reliability.

IV. RESULTS

A. The Characteristics of Tourists

Description of the statistical analysis of results shows that the recoveries of 889 valid questionnaires were collected in this survey, in terms of gender, male 401, and female 481. Mostly in the age to 21-30 years of age, total 437; at least for more than 61 years, a total of two people. In marital status, this married 213, unmarried 567. In educational attainment, the highest for the universities, namely, 496, there is also a Master of 70, at least for the Ph.D, a period of 7. Occupational, mostly students and a total of 406 people, at least for free industry, there are six. In one monthly income, there are highest for \$ NT.20000 total of 244 people, the lowest for more than \$ NT.100001, six people. The number of trips to Penghu, most people first trips to the total of 357 people, at least for more than seven times a total of six people.

B. The Tourists Sources of Travel Information

Description of the statistical analysis of results shows, visitors to the Penghu Islands to engage in tourism activities, the main source of information for the first five: were "friends and family came to Penghu recommended (M=3.93), TV travel programs" (M=3.83), Tourism and Information Science "(M = 3.77), the comments made by users on the internet (M = 3.73), as well as Penghu residents or friends recommended" (M=3.69). From the above results, the information of friends and family recommended and TV travel programs for tourists to Penghu tourism has an impact. More specifically,

newspapers, internet, and tourism information magazine "depth of coverage" for tourists to Penghu, a more in-depth understanding of, is also one of the main sources of travel information. "Friends and family came to Penghu recommended" accounted for the most important sources of information, and interpersonal communication is the biggest impact.

C. The Tourists on Destination Service Satisfaction

Description of the statistical analysis results show that visitors to Penghu engaged in tourism activities, mainly to feel the satisfaction of the top five: order "friendliness of local residents (M = 4.06), local law and order" (M = 4.02) fresh local seafood and delicious "(M=3.97), tourist attractions (M = 3.91), as well as accommodation" (M=3.77). From the above results, we can see Penghu Department of the conditions for the sound development of tourism and visitors to the evaluation are very good. The analysis also found that visitors are not satisfied with the "price cheap" (M=2.55), as well as nightly entertainment selection opportunities (M=2.23). Penghu area, the majority of consumer goods, fruits, etc., are from the Taiwan region; In addition, some seafood industry, regardless of professional ethics, any drive up seafood prices has also been reported. Therefore for Penghu industry, some commodity prices than in Taiwan, more expensive, this is no way things should tourists be stated clearly. In addition, for the industry to drive up seafood prices, the unit in charge of the information of visitors to Penghu description of the pipeline of complaints from tourists encounter unreasonable things, should try to come forward to solve in order to maintain the quality of tourism in Penghu area. Furthermore, nighttime entertainment, the obvious Penghu peak seasons, the coordination of existing industry, to increase the night-time entertainment during the peak season period, to meet the tourists needed.

D. Analysis of Different Demographic Tourists on Travel Information Sources and Services Satisfaction Differences

TABLE I
T-TEST OF DIFFERENT GENDER

Factors	Gender	Frequency	Mean	St	t-value
A	Male	401	23.52	3.72	-2.88*
	Female	481	24.24	3.69	
B	Male	401	21.85	2.41	-2.21*
	Female	481	22.23	2.64	
C	Male	401	11.27	1.72	-.52
	Female	481	11.35	1.71	
D	Male	401	27.43	3.63	-1.32
	Female	481	27.75	3.74	
E	Male	401	14.43	2.18	-2.02*
	Female	481	14.72	2.13	
F	Male	401	11.75	1.71	-.15
	Female	481	11.77	1.65	

*p<.05

According to the results of Table I. t test analysis, source of travel resources, the different gender tourists in the "network and the government information" (t=-2.88, p<.05) and the "mass media" (t=-2.21, p<.05) factors are significant differences, in the "other recommend" (t=-.52, p>.05) factors and no significant difference. Factors in the "network and the government information" from the mean, female (M=24.24) higher than male (M=23.52). Factors in the "mass media", female (M=21.85) higher than male (M=2.23). Service

satisfaction, different gender tourists in the "entertainment and life" (t=-1.32, p>.05) and "resident friendly and good public order" factors (t=-.15, p>.05) no significant differences. However, significant differences exist in the "transportation and public facilities" (t= -2.21, p<.05) factors, from the mean point of view, female (M =14.72) higher than male (M=14.43).

According to the results of the t-test analysis in Table II, the source of travel information, the tourists of different marital status in the "network and the government information" (t=-2.85, p<.05) factors have significant differences, from the mean, the married (M=24.45) than unmarried tourists (M=23.59). In the "mass media" (t=-.86, p <.05) as well as "others recommended" (t=-1.94, p>.05) factors, there are no significant difference. In the service satisfaction, the tourists of different marital status in the "entertainment and life" (t=-1.53, p>.05), "transportation and public facilities" (t=-.78, p>.05), as well as "friendly people and good public order" factor (t= -.69, p>.05) no significant differences.

TABLE II
T-TEST OF DIFFERENT MARITAL

Factors	Marital	Frequency	Mean	St	t-value
A	Marries	213	24.45	3.84	2.85*
	Unmarried	567	23.59	3.72	
B	Marries	213	21.93	2.30	-.86
	Unmarried	567	22.11	2.71	
C	Marries	213	11.15	1.64	-1.94
	Unmarried	567	11.43	1.77	
D	Marries	213	27.92	3.68	1.53
	Unmarried	567	27.47	3.72	
E	Marries	213	14.55	2.19	-.78
	Unmarried	567	14.69	2.11	
F	Marries	213	11.84	1.57	.69
	Unmarried	567	11.76	1.71	

*p<.05

According to the results of Table III One-Way ANOVA analysis, source of travel information, the different age groups of tourists in the "network and the government information" (F=6.53, p<.05) factors have significant differences. Post Hoc results found 31-40 years old, 41-50 years old, 51-60 year old tourist, were higher than the 20 years old of age. "Mass media" (F=.84, p>.05) as well as "others recommended" (F=.85, p>.05) factors and no significant difference. In the service satisfaction, the tourists of different age in the "entertainment and life" (F=1.89, p>.05), "transportation and public facilities" (F=.66, p>.05), and "friendly people and good public order" factor (F=1.44, p>.05) were no significant differences.

Variable in the level of education, according to the results of the analysis, the source of travel information, the tourists in the "network and the government information" (F =1.65, p>.05), the "mass media" (F=1.81, p>.05) as well as "others recommended" (F =1.55, p>.05) factors were no significant differences. In the service satisfaction, the tourists of different levels of education, "entertainment and life" (F=1.79, p>.05), "transportation and public facilities" (F=1.46, p>.05), and "friendly people and good public order" factor (F = 1.85, p>.05) were no significant differences.

Variable in the occupation, according to the results of the analysis, source of travel information, the different age groups of tourists in the "network and the government information" (F=2.98, p<.05) factors have significant differences. Post Hoc results found housekeeper (include retirees), were higher than

freedom and other occupation tourists. "Mass media" (F=1.10, p>.05) as well as "others recommended" (F=1.68, p>.05) factors and no significant difference. In the service satisfaction, the tourists of different occupation in the "entertainment and life" (F=1.28, p>.05), "transportation and public facilities" (F=1.14, p>.05), and "friendly people and good public order" factor (F=.51, p>.05) were no significant differences.

TABLE III
 ONE-WAY ANOVA TEST OF DIFFERENT AGE, EDUCATION, OCCUPATION
 AND INCOME

Variables	Factors	SS	df	MS	F	P	Post Hoc
Age	A	352.73	4	88.18	6.53*	.000	3,4,5>1
	B	21.92	4	5.48	.84	.498	Ns
	C	9.97	4	2.49	.85	.495	Ns
	D	102.78	4	25.69	1.89	.11	Ns
	E	12.22	4	3.06	.66	.623	Ns
	F	16.21	4	4.05	1.44	.217	Ns
Education	A	113.71	5	22.74	1.65	.144	Ns
	B	59.08	5	11.82	1.81	.109	Ns
	C	22.68	5	4.54	1.55	.173	Ns
	D	121.16	5	24.23	1.79	.112	Ns
	E	33.73	5	6.75	1.46	.201	Ns
	F	25.88	5	5.18	1.85	.101	Ns
Occupation	A	399.96	10	39.99	2.98*	.001	6>10,13
	B	72.60	10	7.26	1.10	.361	Ns
	C	49.06	10	4.91	1.68	.081	Ns
	D	172.11	10	17.21	1.28	.238	Ns
	E	53.27	10	5.33	1.14	.327	Ns
	F	14.38	10	1.44	.509	.884	Ns
Income	A	215.63	6	35.94	2.63*	.016	5>6
	B	56.63	6	9.44	1.46	.194	Ns
	C	36.47	6	6.08	2.08*	.054	5>6
	D	225.41	6	37.57	2.80*	.011	7>4
	E	92.06	6	15.34	3.37*	.003	1,7>4
	F	9.31	6	1.55	.55	.768	Ns

*p<.05

Variables in one month income, according to the results of the analysis, the source of travel information, different income tourists "network and government information" (F=2.63, p<.05), and "others recommended" (F=2.08, p<.05) factors have significant differences. However no significant differences in the "mass media" (F=1.46, p>.05) factors. According to the Post Hoc results, income of \$ NT.80-100 thousand of tourists, in a "network with government information" as well as "others recommended" that the two factors are significantly higher than income of \$ NT.101-120 of

tourists. In the service satisfaction, income tourists there are significant differences in the "entertainment and life" (F=2.80, p<.05), "transportation and public facilities" (F=3.37, p<.05). However, in the "friendly people and good public order" factors (F=.55, p>.05), no significant differences exist. According to post hoc results show, that the "entertainment and life" factor, non-income tourists, significantly higher than the \$ NT.40-60 thousand tourists. In the "transportation and public facilities" factor, there are income tourists following of \$ NT.20 thousand and no income, significantly higher than the \$ NT.40-60 thousand tourists.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

A. Conclusion

i. Sources of Travel Information and Destination Service Satisfaction

The results of the analysis found that tourists to Penghu engaged in tourism activities, the main sources of information system in order to: to the Penghu friends and family the most influential, in addition to the TV travel show, as well as newspapers, network and travel intelligence magazine-depth reports are tourists to Penghu's main sources of travel information. In service satisfaction tourist destination, tourists for Penghu residents' friendly degree of law and order, seafood, tourist attractions, as well as accommodation satisfied. But for the service of the local goods price as well as nightly entertainment, tourists think there is still need to improve.

ii. Different Demographic Tourists on Travel Information Sources Differences

Source of travel information, analysis found that female in the "network and the government information" than male. Obviously female are more dependent on the network information, but also to view the pages of the government, in order to better understand the situation of destinations. In addition, in terms of the "mass media" as well as "other recommend" female and male are not significantly different.

On the marital status, the results of the analysis found that married in the "network and the government information" is higher than the unmarried. Obviously, the married are more dependent on the network information, but also to view the pages of the government, in order to better understand the situation of destinations. In addition, the "mass media" as well as "other recommend" the use of married and unmarried persons are not significantly different.

At different ages, found that 31-40 year-old, 41-50 years old, 51-60 years old tourists, in the "network and the government information" is more than 20 years of age tourists. Inference accordingly, ages 20 years of age who will have the result of the source of income are not yet stable, and in this study also found that tourists are students mostly. In addition, the "mass media" as well as "other recommend" different income is not significantly different.

In educational attainment, tourists and not because of differences in educational attainment in the "network and the government information", "mass media" and "other recommend" the use will be significantly different.

Found that occupational housekeeper (include retirees), in "network and the government information" were higher than

freedom and other occupation tourists. Researchers speculate housekeeper (include retirees) more time to fully through the "network and the government information" to collect destination travel information. Other occupation tourists, because the work is less stable, and therefore affect they collect for travel information. But tourists also found different occupations, and will not affect their use of the "mass media" as well as "other recommend".

Finally, in different closing results showed income of \$ NT.80-100 thousand tourists, two factors are significantly higher than the income of more than \$ NT.101 thousand "network and the government information" and that "others recommended" tourists. In fact, the higher income, their living conditions are more stable. Collecting travel information sources, through others, so will produce the above results. However, different income and does not affect the use of tourists for the "Mass media".

iii. Different Demographic Tourists on Services Satisfaction Differences

The analysis of the results shows, service satisfaction, different gender, marital status, age, educational level and occupational tourists for Penghu, "entertainment and life", "transportation and public facilities", as well as "friendly people" factors satisfaction are not significantly different. Additional control of tourists for the Penghu service satisfaction analysis results (see table II), clearly tourists for the Penghu sightseeing service satisfaction are high, not because of a different gender, marital status, age, level of education as well as occupational differences.

On the "entertainment and life" factors in different income, there are non-income tourists, significantly higher than the \$ NT.40-60 thousand tourists. In fact, by the structure of the study sample, the majority of the student majority, and the majority have no income. Their source of income, most rely on home financing, rather than by him-self. So that, their entertainment spending on the more independent applications. Why monthly income NT.40-60 thousand tourists, "entertainment and life" reasons for the lower, should these groups need to burden the family spending and therefore more cautious in terms of consumption. In the "transportation and public facilities" factor, there are followings of \$ NT.20 thousand and no income, significantly higher than the \$ NT.40-60 thousand tourists. In fact, the reason the entertainment and life "of similar results, lower income, in addition to the supply source of income is the family, there are some other people own work the money. But these part-time the money earned, and not entirely for the necessities of life, the majority of more than used for entertainment and living expenses. And other living expenses, from family, so spend more convenient. Finally, the "friendly people" factors, the results of the analysis found that different income tourists are the same satisfaction in this regard. So obviously can be learned, the tourists that Penghu local residents are very friendly for tourists, not exclusion tourists.

B. Suggestion

i. Practical Suggestion for Tourism Management

From the results of the analysis, the source of travel information, for Penghu's tourism unit in charge of the industry that allows Penghu, tourists have a good travel experience, the future for the recommendation of the Penghu area tourism, are also likely give a positive recommendation. Seen the Department of Penghu has good conditions of developing tourism, and tourists of the evaluation are very good. But the analysis also found that visitors are not satisfied with "cheap price" and "night entertainment choice". Thus, the Penghu tourism-related units, the prices in the region should no longer attach importance to, whether with or without suspected of price gouging. Furthermore, nighttime entertainment, the obvious Penghu peak seasons, the coordination of existing industry, to increase the night-time entertainment during the peak season period, to meet the tourists needed. In fact, from the tourists "behavioral intention" of the most influential of the three factors (others recommend, entertainment and life functions, as well as transportation and public facilities) point of view, Penghu local tourism industry and relevant units to good service, improve and perfect the public living facilities and complementary leisure and recreational activities to enhance the reputation of tourists, and to retain existing visitors, and can recommend to others and then through the existing visitors and to enhance the number of tourists in Penghu.

ii. For Further Research

In this study, manpower and funding factors, and select only the Penghu Islands to study, did not then continue to analyze the quality of service of the tourists on the other Islands in the Taiwan region, it is suggested that future researchers can then compare the situation in other waters. In addition, this study and no specific analysis of tourists to participate in the waters, as well as compare the different activities involved in the differences, so follow-up study of think about this aspect, and can increase the research variables to be more specific understanding of the other impact of tourism the case of customer service quality, satisfaction feeling.

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